

Paper 17

LANDSCAPE OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT**Purpose:**

The study throws light on the legislative policies and programs prepared for the adults on their skill development.

Methodology / Design / Approaches: It is an exploratory study with the help of secondary data where the researchers have conducted a content analysis of various policies and programmes on skill development of adults.

Findings and results: Providing fresh Skill Developmental training to School Dropouts, College Dropouts, and Unemployed Adults motivating their skills available the current activities, and providing opportunities for dropout Adults. To know the Governmental scheme for getting job opportunities by improving their skill. This study shows that opportunities are provided to Adults to know utilizing for their skill development.

Originality/value: Content analysis over the policies and programmes on skill development of the adults in India

Type of Paper: Descriptive research with exploratory research design.

Keywords: Skill Development, Policies on Skill Development, Skill development Programmes, Adult development programmes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Skill development programmes help people to build their professional ability and networking with better Communication, Skill and expertise. Skills are known to be the abilities which could be acquired through practice. Skill training help people to identify their skill gap and nurturing their innate talents in desired ways so as to be self-reliant and productive. Skill development enables youth to globalize their abilities and competencies. In India, adults use skill development programmes for upskilling themselves for seeking better employment opportunities. Youth population is identified in the Society for their unique ways of life. Skill ecosystem of the country refers to the contextual framework relating to policies, models of engaging workforce, job structure and level of expertise of the labour class. The study of skill ecosystem is essential to know the existing skill gap of Indian workforce. Skill development in next 30 years for the progress of the country depends on the training youths aged between 18 to 35 years. The widespread digital technology seeks multitasking workforce employed by the specialized recruiters. The need for digital literacy in 21st Century with technical skills on emerging

technologies will become the competitive advantage. Young generation should be trained to adopt technology at work for ease of doing things. Emotional quotient, social intelligence, creativity, innovative mindset has become parameters to achieve success in the 21st Century. The most of the young population in India is between 18-30 years of age group. According to the World Health Organization adult is a person who is older than 19 years of Age. For the skill development of working population in the country both Central and State Governments have initiated several initiatives. In India, the concept of Skill Development was introduced post-independence in 1956 with the first Industrial Policy which had an initial focus on formal Technical and Vocational Training Education and Training (TVET) sector with dedicated institutions for technical and vocational education. In 1961, the Apprenticeship Act was framed for providing practical training to technically qualified persons in various trades and promoting new skilled manpower. The Indian Education Commission (Kothari Commission) was appointed in 1964 to overhaul the Indian Education Sector by providing policies & guidelines for the development of education in India. The National Labour Policy was framed in 1966. In 1968, the first National Policy on Education was framed. The first Industrial Training Institute (ITI) was set up in 1969 by the Ministry of Labour & Employment (MoLE), Government of India. New National Policy of Education was framed in 1986. The All-India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) was formed in 1987, as the official regulator and funder for polytechnics and technical colleges. The National Policy of Education was modified in 1992. 1990s witnessed the opening up of the economy with substantial growth in IT industry and service sector and relative slowdown in manufacturing and engineering sector. It was felt that a considerable amount of employment for skilled and semi-skilled category workers was to be explored outside the traditional trades. With this objective, the National Development Corporation (NSDC) was established in 2008. This paradigm shift resulted in framing of the first National Policy on Skill Development in 2009 and effort was made to enhance the private partnership to expand the capacity of skills training sector. The National Skills Development Agency (NSDA) was established in 2013 and a vision was casted for a National Qualification Framework (NQF). In 2014, the Apprenticeship Act was amended to include non-engineering as optional trades and Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) was established. In 2015, the Skill India Mission was launched, the National Policy on Skill Development and Entrepreneurship was framed and the Training and Apprenticeship Division was moved from MoLE to MSDE.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

This paper describes the fundamentals of skill development in India. It enlists various programmes and policies framed by the government on skill development initiatives. It suggests the challenges and directs the readers to the future course of action to fill the skill gap in the country.

4. RELATED WORK:

The conceptual analysis is derived based on the search results of Google Scholar by using available literature in the areas of “skill development of the adults in India” by referring to the published works between 2012 to 2022

Sl. No	Area of Study	Observation	Reference
1	Skill Development for Employability	Skills determine the employment	Behera, B., & Gaur, D. M. (2021)[1].
2	Investment on Improving Demographic Dividend	There is a shortage of skilled labour force.	Mishra, N. (2016) [2]
3	Out come of Vocationally Trained Population	The demand for Vocational Education is more than the Secondary Education	Agrawal, T., & Agrawal, A. (2017) [3].
4	Vocational Education	Higher Wage is paid to the Vocational education holder	Agrawal, T [4].
5	Developing employability skills by education	Education should concentrate on Upskilling the Students	Seema Pandey (2016) [5].
6	Current labour market for Vocational Training	Labour market is wide open for the Skilled persons.	Agrawal, T. (2014) [6].
7	The role of Non-formal education on Skill development towards national progress.	Skilled employees contributed from technical institutes earn a good life early compared to regular education students.	Jha, B., Goswami, V., & Surana, A. (2013) [7]
8	Integrating vocation and general education	Need to be brought under the National Skill Qualification Framework	Mehrotra, V. S. (2016) [8].
9	Vocational and Literacy Skill development	Vocational and Literary skills leads for entrepreneurship	Yadav, R. (2018) [9].
10	Make in India	Reduce the gap between available skill and desired skill	Deka, R. J., & Batra, B. (2016) [10].
11	Problems of formal education in addressing the human resource development	Vocationalisation of education can fill the Gap	Akram, M. (2012) [11].
12	Investing on Skill Development	Indian demography is unequally distributed across the country	Afroz, Z. (2018) [12].
13	Gram Tarang Employability Training Services	Vocational education need to be dynamic	Mishra, M. (2014) [13].

14	Skill Development Policies	National Training Fund need to be constituted	Sharma, H. (2017) [14].
15	National Policy on Skill Development and Entrepreneurship 2015	Effective Institutional framework to achieve the goal of policy is the need.	Barua, R. (2017) [15].

5. EVOLUTION OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

In India, during post-independence, skill development was introduced under the Industrial Policy of 1956 by introducing opportunity to get formal Technical, Vocational Education and Training from exclusive educational institutions. The Apprenticeship Act 1961 made provisions to provide practical trainings to technically qualifying persons in several trades to add newly skilled manpower. The Indian Education Commission 1964 provided policies & guidelines for the development of technical and vocational education in India. The National Labour Policy was introduced in 1966. The first Industrial Training Institute (ITI) was constituted in 1969 under the Ministry of Labour and Employment, Government of India. Under the National Policy of Education 1968, All India Council of Technical Education was framed in 1987. The National Policy on education is modified in 1992 to provide Polytechnic and Technical Colleges in India. 1990's witnessed the opening of economy with substantial growth in IT industry and service sectors with relative slowdown in manufacturing and engineering sector. The National Development Corporation was established in 2008. The National Policy for Skill Development was constituted in 2009. Effort are made to increase the Private Partnership to expand the capacity of skill Training sector. The National Skill Development Agency was established in 2013 giving way for National Qualification Framework by 2014. Government of India has provided National Policy on Skill Development to leverage the supply of skilled workforce to industries. Under 11th five-year plan, government focused to train annually 15 million people so as to achieve skilled workforce of 500 million by 2022. Indian Skill Development Service Rules, 2017 was enacted. National Literacy Mission for Adult education and skill development which is a Centrally Sponsored scheme. In order to support NGO's and Institutions on Adult Education and Skill Development, Saakshar Bharat scheme was introduced. Capacity Building Scheme mainly focus on youth who are unemployed and helps in developing their skills on entrepreneurship. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) a Centrally sponsored scheme 2016-2020 is a grant-based scheme providing free-of-cost skill development training and skill certification. It is an initiative to create Standard Infrastructure for the delivery of skill development training on industry relevant courses. To ensure the employment, Rozgar Mela was introduced. National Skill Development Corporation under the aegis of Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, Government of India. Udaan is an initiative to address the needs of educated unemployed in Jammu and Kashmir who are graduated, post graduated and three years diploma engineers to provide skill and job opportunities. Skill India comprises of training programmes such as training in Agriculture where training is given on agricultural implements, soil conservation training center etc. Startup policy for the technical institution was constituted. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana by technical institutions was implemented through AICTE-approved colleges to impart engineering skills to drop-out students. Jan Shikshan Sanstha (JSS), National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS), and Craftsmen Training

Scheme (CTS), Employability Enhancement Training Programme (EETT), National Employability Enhancement Mission (NEEM), AICTE-Startup Policy, Skill Assessment Matrix for Vocational Advancement of Youth (SAMVAY), Leaders Development Programme, etc. are the key plans and programmes in this regard.

6. CHALLENGES ON SKILL DEVELOPMENT:

In Indian context, facilities are available but practical opportunities are lacking. There are many schemes and programmes offered from the Central Government but, there is no proper platform to exercise the facilities. The challenge is with the rural population living in the rural area where many are not getting facilities to upskill themselves. Lack of education is stopping them from forming local rural governance. It is a new challenge for the employers to develop new skills or updating skills even. Youth is interested on entrepreneurship [16]. Education is equal for all but the success depends upon their individual abilities [17].

7. CONCLUSION:

Government has several Policies and Schemes for Adult but all programmes are not utilised well because of lack of skills among them. The young generation is not fully potential since, many are addicted to drugs and other activities. Self-employment might be the break through. Adults drop out of skills and college which is the first set back. In order to provide opportunity for the dropout students, skill development training programmes are offered. National Skill Development is encouraged to enhance the abilities of the youth [18], skill development and self-reliance [19]. The issues connected to the absence of Vocational Education, unique training standards, efforts to reduce the dropout ratio, qualified trainers, systematic monitoring and evaluation system need to be improved to nurture the demographic dividend of the Country [20].

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